

METHODOLOGY FOR CHARACTERIZING THE FIBER PRINT THROUGH AND OVERALL SURFACE QUALITY FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Marc O. Voltz^{1*}, Olaf Zöllner², and Peter Mitschang³

¹ Covestro Deutschland AG, Leverkusen, Germany, marc.voltz@covestro.com, www.covestro.com

² Covestro Deutschland AG, Leverkusen, Germany, olaf.zoellner@covestro.com, www.covestro.com

³ Leibniz-Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe, Kaiserslautern, Germany, peter.mitschang@ivw.uni-kl.de, www.ivw.uni-kl.de

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ABSTRACT

Surface quality is a critical issue for thermoplastic composites in technical and aesthetic applications. One of the most prominent effects on composite surfaces is the fiber print through, a visible pattern corresponding with the fiber directions in the laminate. Although this has been discussed in literature in the past, there is no unified approach for the characterization of fiber print through. This paper shows the development of such an approach and elaborates the necessary steps including determination of measuring area, resolution and relevant key figures. A set of laminates with varying amounts of fiber print through and pores was analyzed with the developed method to show the expressiveness and validate the approach. The derived framework can be customized for the analysis of different material combinations and constitutions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber print through (FPT) is a characteristic surface appearance for continuous fiber reinforced plastics (cFRP). On unidirectional (UD) laminates it is a surface pattern of superimposed lines that correspond to the fiber directions of the plies. The FPT of the top layer is the most dominant and the effect of each subsequent layer decreases (Figure 1). It is mainly caused by the different thermo-mechanic behavior of the fibers and matrix and can be influenced by material constitution and processing [1–4].

Figure 1: Fiber print through (FPT) on unidirectional composites visible for top (0°) and lower layers (90°)

This phenomenon is highly relevant for visible and aesthetic applications considering surface quality requirements. The surface of UD laminates has a quasi-periodic nature due to the alternating occurrence of fiber-rich and matrix-rich areas which is not as regular as for woven fabric reinforced laminates due to the lack of discrete threads but also not completely randomized due to the directionality of the UD plies. Standard approaches according to the ISO framework on geometric product specifications are not adequate to characterize FPT, because they do not account for its specific size and geometric properties. Being able to describe FPT quantitatively is required for targeted material and process optimization to

reduce the effect. This work addresses the development of a characterization method for FPT on UD cFRP to achieve objective and comparable key figures on the example of a flat laminate made from polycarbonate (PC) and UD carbon fibers (CF) with plies in 0° and 90° . To evaluate FPT, the laminate surface must be measured with a suitable measuring method and then described qualitatively and quantitatively. The measurement method must be able to record and distinguish the relevant structural variables for the effect of FPT, both in terms of area and in relation to profile heights. Regarding industrial application, attention shall be paid to the economic efficiency of the method. The measurement resolution should be selected in such a way that the required level of detail is achieved with the lowest possible measurement effort and thus also the shortest possible measurement time.

2 STATE OF THE ART

The evaluation of FPT has been a topic of scientific literature from two main viewpoints, aesthetic applications on one hand and composite mirror manufacturing for space applications on the other. The common objective of both fields is the quantification of the FPT and consecutively optimizing the clarity of reflected images from a surface. This leads to similar approaches for measurement and evaluation but there has not been a clear trend towards a unified approach or even a specific framework for UD composites.

The used measuring techniques include tactile stylus profilometers [2, 5, 6], white light profilometers [3, 4, 7], laser or white light interferometers [8–10] and laser scanning microscopes [11]. The measuring length or field, so called region of interest (ROI), for the measurement is chosen either according to the given values in the standards or due to considerate choice based on geometric properties of the surface. Typical for the latter are the consideration of the dominant or largest structure size to be investigated, e.g. threads in woven fabrics [3, 4] or fiber agglomerates in UD laminates [8].

In most cases linear key figures for roughness (R-parameters) and waviness (W-parameters) based on ISO standards 4287 are extracted from the measurements. Most commonly used parameters are the arithmetic mean deviation of the assessed profile R_a and W_a , the root mean square deviation of the assessed profile R_q and W_q , the total height of profile R_t and W_t within the evaluation length (the whole measured line) and the maximum height of profile R_z and W_z within a sampling length (part of the evaluation length) [2–7, 9, 10, 12]. R_z and W_z are sometimes referred to as R_{zDIN} and W_{zDIN} , which is not according to the ISO standard, the same applies for R_{max} and W_{max} . [10]. Less represented are averaged parameters like W_{z25} calculated as an average of W_z in an array of 5×5 ROIs [3, 4] and areal surface parameters from ISO 25178 like the arithmetic mean height S_a and the maximum height S_z [11]. In many cases, information about the data processing or parametrization of the necessary filter operations are missing. The lack thereof presents a challenge for benchmarking the methods, because these choices can influence the resulting surface key figures [3, 4]. The distinction of roughness and waviness is a mere definition of a threshold and whether the size of surface features is below or above it. This means that it is highly dependent on the actual size of fibers or bundles thereof causing FPT on a given laminate. Missing parametrization and description of the estimated structure size prevent the proper evaluation of expressiveness of the determined figures.

3 MATERIALS

This investigation uses a subset of specimen produced for a study to determine processing and layup related influences on the surface of UD CF/PC [1]. The study design included center groups, where all parameters were set to the medium factor value. This resulted in 12 specimens (S-01 to S-12) with UD layers in 0° and 90° orientation which were all produced under the same conditions. This allows a good comparison of the measured surfaces and enables to highlight the distinct characteristics of each specimen.

4 MEASUREMENT

FPT can be understood as an areal phenomenon or as a superimposition of linear phenomena in the

different directions of layer orientation. Therefore, we chose areal measurements to account for both aspects. In order to avoid damaging the surface and to achieve the required accuracy, optical measurements with a chromatic white light profilometer (WLP), in our case a FRT MicroProf 200 manufactured by FormFactor, were chosen. The WLP features a traversing table which holds the specimen and moves it along a fixed chromatic white light (CWL) sensor which measures the surface topography (see Table 1 for technical data). A white light point focused on the specimen surface after being sent through strongly wavelength-dependent focal length optics. The spectrum of the light reflected at the surface shows a peak, which corresponds to the strongest reflected wavelength. This allows calculation of the distance between the sensor and the focus point (see Figure 2).

Property	Value
Measuring range	600 μm
Max. resolution z	6 nm
Max. resolution x, y	2 μm
Repeatability	$< 0.00009 \times \text{ROI}$
Accuracy	$< 0.00033 \times \text{ROI} + 0.001 \times \text{measuring height}$

Table 1: Technical data of the CWL sensor used for the measurements [13]

Figure 2: Specimen during WLP measurement (left) and working principle CWL sensor [13] (right)

The measurement consists of consecutive line scans in a defined spacing which are then aggregated to represent the areal topography of the specimen. In our case, the individual lines are scanned in x-direction and then the y-axis advances for the next line. The specimens are aligned with the 0° fiber direction of the top layer parallel to the y-axis of the machine, so the scans are performed perpendicular to that direction. The ROI should accommodate the biggest relevant surface feature at least five times (ISO 25178-3) [14]. In the case of the used UD PC/CF laminates the maximum feature size is approx. 2.5 mm, which was determined by explorative measurements. In order to accommodate at least five periods in both 0° and 90°, the ROI was set to an area of 12.5 mm x 12.5 mm. To compensate for inaccuracies in specimen alignment and allow rotating and cutting the sampled area was enlarged by another period to 15 mm x 15 mm.

The WLP scans the surface with a single measuring point, so the duration of a measurement increases at least quadratically with the lateral resolution (without considering the traverse movements before starting a new line). Reducing the resolution to the minimal feasible level ensures efficient capture of relevant surface features in the least amount of time. To determine the minimal lateral resolution, we used a concept already applied by Hildebrandt for woven fabric reinforced laminates [3]. The human

eye can only distinguish structural elements such as the lines of FPT down to a certain lateral distance, below which it can only identify them as surface roughness or a reduction of the gloss behavior. This depends on the angular resolution capability and the viewing distance.

The angular resolution capability of the human eye $\Delta\phi$ typically is about one arc minute ($1'$). As this value can be superseded an angle of $0.75'$ is chosen as a reference. The viewing distance l depends on the application in focus, ranging from a few centimeters, e.g. for consumer goods like laptops, up to multiple meters, e.g. for automotive exterior parts. Since smaller distances also lead to improved spatial resolution of the eye, a minimum viewing distance of 0.2 m was chosen as a basis for further evaluations. The distance d that two structural elements must be apart so that the eye still perceives them as separate structures can be calculated by the following equation resulting from the geometric relations:

$$d = 2l \tan\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{2}\right) \quad (1)$$

Considering the chosen values for l and $\Delta\phi$, d calculates as $44 \mu\text{m}$. To avoid aliasing the measurement should at least oversample the surface five times (ISO 25178-3) and therefore a lateral resolution of $8 \mu\text{m}$ was chosen. This results in a grid of 1876×1876 scanned points on the ROI.

5 DATA EVALUATION

The measured surface topography, represented by an array of height values z over the x and y coordinates, was processed with Digital Surf MountainsMap® (Digital Surf SARL, Besançon, France). The workflow consists of data clean-up, filtering and derivation of surface key figures. The clean-up includes several steps to account for effects caused by the material and the measurement itself like removal of outliers and measuring noise, infill of non-measured points, line levelling, curvature removal with pore exclusion, alignment of the texture direction to the coordinate system and cropping to final dimension. The topography is filtered with a Gaussian filter (ISO 16610-61) with a nesting index of 0.8 mm to exclude large scale areal features (e.g. large area sink marks) and focus on the FPT (

Figure 3). The nesting index was chosen to achieve an appropriate representation of the visual effect of FPT on the measured specimen after a sensitivity analysis. This can vary for different material constitutions.

Figure 3: Surface topography (top view) after clean-up and filtering, clearly showing FPT

The filtered surface is used to extract surface key figures, including areal parameters derived from ISO 25178 as well as linear parameters derived from the recently released ISO 21920 which replaces the old ISO 4287. While the calculation of parameters remains mainly untouched, the new standard homogenizes the approach for linear surface characterization with the one for areal surfaces from ISO 25178 and it emphasizes the specification of the used nesting index to clarify the evaluation conditions more clearly. The areal parameters are S_q (root-mean-square height, integrated over ROI surface area A and normalized afterwards, equation 2) to describe the overall surface evenness, S_z (maximum height, distance between lowest and highest z value in the ROI) to evaluate the severity of localized imperfections like pores and S_{ku} (kurtosis, integrated over ROI surface area A , normalized by A and fourth power of S_q , equation 3) to describe the height distribution curve.

$$S_q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{A} \iint_A z(x,y) dx dy} \quad (2)$$

$$S_{ku} = \frac{1}{S_q^4} \frac{1}{A} \iint_A z^4(x,y) dx dy \quad (3)$$

S_q and S_z are height parameters and therefore expressed in μm , whereas S_{ku} is dimensionless. S_q and S_{ku} integrate the individual height values z over the surface area A of the ROI and normalized after integration. The linear parameters are used to describe the FPT of different layer orientations and are extracted perpendicular to each fiber direction in the laminate. We chose R_q (root-mean-square height, integrated over the profile length l_m and normalized) measured perpendicular to the fiber directions in the laminate. To compensate for outliers due to irregularities (e.g. pores) we averaged the R_q values from a set of ten linear profiles evenly spaced throughout the ROI. The resulting values are referred to as $R_{q\theta}$, with θ being the referred to the angle of fiber direction with respect to the outermost layer (equation 4).

$$R_{q\theta} = \frac{1}{10} \sum_{i=1}^{10} \sqrt{\frac{1}{l_m} \int_{l_m} z(x)^2 dx} \quad (4)$$

$R_{q\theta}$ then describes the FPT caused by the fibers aligned in the respective direction. In our case, with 0° and 90° layers, we look at R_{q0° and R_{q90° . If the investigated laminates had different fiber directions θ , according $R_{q\theta}$ values could be calculated as well to describe their impact on the surface. It is important to note, that the scale of R_q in this context cannot be compared directly to other roughness measurements according to ISO 4287, as the nesting index of the Gaussian filter is chosen to fit the structure size of the FPT pattern and not as stated in the old standard.

6 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Figure 4 provides an overview of all captured and filtered surface profiles. Note that for better visibility the z scale of each surface plot is individually optimized for maximum contrast instead of maintaining a common scale. The graphical representation clearly shows the distinct linear pattern of FPT for all specimens in varying severity. Also, some of the specimen have smaller or bigger pores in different amounts. The determined key figures (Table 2) reflect that situation with a range of different combinations of values. The colours in the table were assigned to each column for easier comparison, ranging from green for the minimum, white for the median and red for the maximum.

Specimen	Layup	S_q [μm]	S_z [μm]	S_{ku} [-]	$R_{q 0^\circ}$ [μm]	$R_{q 90^\circ}$ [μm]
S-01	[0/90/0/0] _s	0.219	6.054	8.711	0.206	0.151
S-02		0.214	8.609	112.042	0.186	0.141
S-03		0.168	5.407	9.428	0.158	0.119
S-04		0.182	7.408	17.660	0.178	0.127
S-05		0.180	5.332	17.456	0.170	0.119
S-06		0.171	12.293	192.704	0.170	0.097
S-07	[0/0/90/0] _s	0.159	2.290	3.914	0.151	0.105
S-08		0.154	11.297	174.349	0.143	0.094
S-09		0.140	2.731	4.625	0.147	0.114
S-10		0.261	9.536	134.078	0.231	0.168
S-11		0.209	11.355	150.777	0.187	0.139
S-12		0.195	13.610	263.619	0.163	0.120

Table 2: Measured surface parameters (colour range green-white-red from lowest to highest value in each column)

Figure 4: Overview of the filtered surface profiles (height scale adjusted for maximum contrast)

S_q considers all measured points and weighs them quadratically, so it gives a general overview of the surface quality, the lower S_q the flatter the overall topography. This means laminates with lower FPT and fewer pores have lower S_q values and vice versa (Figure 5). Isolated, it does not give any information about the distribution of height values or the amount or extent of localized defects. However, the latter influence S_q as it is quadratically weighted, which means surfaces with pores have higher S_q values.

Figure 5: Lowest (S-09, left) and highest (S-10, right) observed S_q values

S_z can provide additional information on surface constitution, as it puts the S_q values into perspective by considering the difference between the overall lowest and highest measured points. Figure 6 presents a comparison of the S_q and S_z values for all specimens. Considering these two factors, they can be divided in four groups: Low S_q and S_z (S-07, S-09), which indicates a low amount of FPT and no significant pores. Low/medium S_q and high S_z (S-06, S-08, S-12) is an indicator of low FPT with at least one deep pore. For medium S_q and S_z (S-01, S-03, S-04, S-05) the expressiveness is a bit more ambiguous. While the medium S_z indicates the presence of pores, the medium S_q can be the result of either more severe FPT or a larger number of pores that enlarge the value. Medium/high S_q and high S_z (S-02, S-10, S-11) as the last group also show the same ambiguity, the combination of only these two values remains inconclusive here.

Figure 6: Comparison of S_q and S_z values

This is where the comparison between S_z and S_{ku} becomes relevant. Both parameters appear to be correlated for the measured surfaces (Figure 7). As S_{ku} is calculated with the topography height value as a fourth power in its formula it has a much wider range of values than the other considered parameters. It is sensitive to localized features like pores and particularly their severeness and amount. S_{ku} considers every occurrence of these geometry features and weighs them with the respective S_q value of the surface. This gives additional information of the surface constitution in comparison to the most often exclusively used S_z or even R_t values as these only represent the difference between the highest and lowest measured points on the surface. S-02 and S-04 provide a good example for the expressiveness of S_{ku} . Both specimens feature similar S_q and S_z values, but their S_{ku} differs by a substantial extent. Looking at the pictures of both specimens they feature similar FPT and overall surface quality with pores of the same sizes, but the number of pores is significantly higher on S-02 (Figure 8). In contrast, surfaces with similar S_z and S_{ku} can have a deviating appearance. This can be seen on specimens S-08 and S-11, which feature S_{ku} values in a similar range and near identical S_z but S_q of S-08 being about 27 % lower (Figure 9). This means S_{ku} has to be seen as an auxiliary value to add information about the amount and severeness of localized defects.

Figure 7: Comparison of S_z and S_{ku} values

Figure 8: High (S-02, left) vs. low (S-04, right) number of pores on otherwise similar surfaces

Figure 9: Deviation in appearance of surfaces with similar S_z and S_{ku} , S-08 (left) and S-011 (right)

$R_{q\ 0^\circ}$ and $R_{q\ 90^\circ}$ were chosen as parameters to evaluate FPT for each laminate direction separately. Comparing them to S_q , all values show high correlation to each other, with $R_{q\ 0^\circ}$ being 7% and $R_{q\ 90^\circ}$ 33% lower than S_q in average (Figure 10). The close match between S_q and R_q can be attributed to FPT being a 2.5-dimensional phenomenon for each UD layer with distinct characteristics perpendicular to the fiber direction. This remains mostly unchanged along the fiber path in the considered scale of the ROI. FPT in the 0° direction is the most dominant surface topography feature upon visible inspection and the match of S_q and $R_{q\ 0^\circ}$ shows good correlation to that effect. As FPT of the lower layers becomes less severe the

further they are from the surface, the lower $R_q 90^\circ$ values appear plausible as well. As the difference in $R_q 90^\circ$ values between the specimen is quite small, a visual distinction of different levels becomes more difficult (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Comparison of S_q and R_q values

Figure 11: High vs. low $R_q 90^\circ$, S-04 (left) and S-06 (right)

These findings indicate that $R_q 0^\circ$ could be considered an estimator for S_q for UD laminates with slight deviation towards lower values. The deviation is most likely related to the fact that S_q considers the whole surface with all localized defects, which lead to higher values, while the ten lines used to calculate the averaged $R_q 0^\circ$ do not necessarily hit those defects, which leads to lower values. However, if by chance one of the lines lies within a pore R_q will be greatly increased by that. In practice this means if the existence of pores and other localized effects is sorted out by other quality control measures and the focus lies on quantifying FPT, only measuring the linear parameters is a viable option to cut down measuring time significantly.

7 SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

This paper showed the development and evaluation of a procedure to evaluate FPT and overall surface quality on laminates made from UD tape. It provides meaningful, objective key figures that enable data-based comparison and statistical analysis of UD laminate surfaces exhibiting FPT. The considerations for the measuring setup to efficiently capture the surface topography in a suitable scale and resolution have been shown as well as the evaluation process to make use of the captured data. A set of key figures calculated according to ISO 25178 and ISO 21920 has been chosen to describe the

relevant aspects of FPT, the evaluation of overall surface appearance and the amount and extent of localized defects like pores. Especially the consideration of the kurtosis S_{ku} is a novel approach to describe the specific characteristics of UD composite surfaces which has not been done in scientific literature. The procedure can be generalized and used as a framework for the analysis of other material combinations, e.g. glass fibers and other polymers (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Framework for characterization of FPT and overall surface quality for UD laminates

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REFERENCES

- [1] Voltz, M O ; Zöllner, O ; Mitschang, P: Effects of Thermoforming Parameters on Surface Quality of Unidirectional Reinforced Amorphous Thermoplastic Composites. *Proceedings ITHEC 2022, 6th International Conference and Exhibition on Thermoplastic Composites*. Bremen, Germany : CONGRESS BREMEN, M3B GmbH, Germany, 2022 — ISBN 978-3-933339-33-1, S. 72–75
- [2] Lin, Huei-Jeng ; Liao, Chin-I. ; Jiang, Ren-Li ; Kuo, Yan-Min: Print-through phenomenon on the surface of GFRP: pilot study. In: *Journal of composite materials* Bd. 41, Sage Publications Sage UK: London, England (2007), Nr. 26, S. 3055–3078
- [3] Hildebrandt, Klaus: *Material- und prozessspezifische Einflüsse auf Oberflächeneigenschaften von endlosfaserverstärkten Thermoplasten* [Dissertation]. Technische Universität Kaiserslautern, 2015
- [4] Hildebrandt, Klaus ; Schulte-Hubbart, Felix ; Medina, Luisa ; Mitschang, Peter: Influence of fabric parameters on surface waviness of FRPC: an experimental investigation and development of a model on surface waviness. In: *Applied Science and Engineering Progress* Bd. 8 (2015), Nr. 1, S. 1–10
- [5] Lin, Huei-Jeng ; Liao, Chin-I. ; Jiang, Ren-Li: Methods to Reduce the Print-through Phenomenon on the Surface of FRP. In: *Journal of reinforced plastics and composites* Bd. 26, Sage Publications Sage CA: Thousand Oaks, CA (2007), Nr. 4, S. 377–389

- [6] Kuo, Yan-Min ; Lin, Huei-Jeng ; Lee, Yi-Hsiu ; Lai, Wei-Ming: Study of the decrease in print-through phenomenon on fiber-reinforced plastic material. In: *Journal of reinforced plastics and composites* Bd. 30, SAGE Publications Sage UK: London, England (2011), Nr. 24, S. 1989–2001
- [7] Kraemer, M ; Middendorf, P ; Bauernhansl, T: Investigation on the influence of humidity on the topography of surfaces of polymeric class A carbon fiber reinforced plastics. In: *Journal of Composite Materials* Bd. 52 (2018), Nr. 30, S. 4247–4260
- [8] Hochhalter, Jake D. ; Massarello, Jack J. ; Maji, Arup K. ; Fuierer, Paul A.: The origins of fiber print-through in lightweight composite optics. *Novel Optical Systems Design and Optimization IX*. Bd. 6289 : International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2006, S. 628902
- [9] Koyanagi, Jun ; Arao, Yoshihiko ; Utsunomiya, Shin ; Takeda, Shin-ichi ; Kawada, Hiroyuki: High accurate space telescope mirror made by light and thermally stable CFRP. In: *Journal of Solid Mechanics and Materials Engineering* Bd. 4, The Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers (2010), Nr. 11, S. 1540–1549
- [10] Guedes, Joana F. ; Martins, Marta SS ; Martins, Ramiro ; Rocha, Nuno: Carbon Nanotube Layer for Reduction of Fiber Print-Through in Carbon Fiber Composites. In: *Advances in Polymer Technology* Bd. 2019, Hindawi (2019)
- [11] Lück, André: *Oberflächenoptimierung endlosfaserverstärkter Thermoplaste* [Dissertation]. Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 2020
- [12] Shiou, Fang-Jung ; Lai, Yao-Zih ; Tsai, Min-Long: Development of a lightweight portable optical measurement system for the print-through phenomenon of fiber-reinforced plastics. *Seventh International Symposium on Precision Engineering Measurements and Instrumentation*. Bd. 8321 : International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2011, S. 83213C
- [13] FRT GmbH: Technical Datasheet CWL Chromatic White Light Sensor.
- [14] DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V.: DIN EN ISO 25178-3 – Geometrical product specifications (GPS) – Surface texture: Areal – Part 3: Specification operators (ISO 25178-3:2012); English version EN ISO 25178-3:2012, English translation of DIN EN ISO 25178-3:2012-11.